

Nutritional and Phytochemical Characterization of *Terminalia catappa* Hulls: An Underutilized Resource for Sustainable Food Systems and Ecosystem Resilience

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Abstract

The tropical almond tree (*Terminalia catappa*) is a versatile perennial plant renowned for its resilience to saline and sandy soils and untapped nutritional potential. Despite the kernel's established health benefits, the fruit's hull remains under-researched. This study aimed to evaluate the nutritional and phytochemical composition of *T. catappa* hulls collected from three locations in Lagos State, Nigeria. Standard procedures were used to determine the proximate composition (moisture, protein, lipid, ash, crude fibre, and carbohydrate), mineral contents and the qualitative and quantitative phytochemical properties of the collected hull samples. Statistical significance was established using ANOVA ($p < 0.05$). This study revealed significant moisture ($71.88 \pm 0.07\%$), carbohydrate ($24.32 \pm 0.05\%$), and crude fibre ($2.80 \pm 0.05\%$) contents in *Terminalia catappa* hulls, along with the presence of phenolic compounds exhibiting antioxidant potential. Notable phytochemicals identified included flavonoids, tannins, and terpenoids, supporting their functional food potential. Additionally, the hulls contained a high concentration of vitamin C that surpasses many common fruits and exceeds the daily recommended dietary allowances for adults (60 mg), offering potential antioxidant benefits. The study highlights the nutritional and bioactive richness of *T. catappa* hulls, advocating for their inclusion in food systems to enhance dietary diversity and sustainability. Promoting the utilisation of *T. catappa* could aid in addressing food insecurity and fostering agricultural biodiversity in resource-constrained regions while contributing to ecosystem stability.

Keywords: Hull, kernel, nutrition, phytochemicals, *Terminalia catappa*.

1.0 Introduction

The tropical almond tree (*Terminalia catappa*), commonly known as Indian almond, sea almond, or Malabar almond, is a perennial plant that is widely distributed across tropical and subtropical regions, with origins in South and Southeast Asia [1]. This robust tree, belonging to the Combretaceae family, thrives in coastal regions and is notable for its tolerance to saline and sandy soils [2, 3]. It serves multiple purposes, such as providing shade during warmer months and being used as an orchard crop or an ornamental addition to landscapes [3]. *T. catappa* also possesses promising nutritional and economic values that have remained largely untapped [1].

The tree produces a unique fruit, featuring a fleshy exterior and a hard shell that encloses an edible,

nutrient-dense seed or kernel often referred to as the tropical almond. This kernel stands out for its high concentration of healthy fats, particularly unsaturated fatty acids such as oleic and linoleic acids, which are beneficial for cardiovascular health [4]. Beyond its fat content, the kernel also supplies significant protein, dietary fibre, and essential vitamins and minerals, including vitamins E and B, zinc, magnesium, and calcium [4, 5]. The presence of bioactive compounds like flavonoids and tannins further enhances its health benefits, as these compounds have antioxidant properties that support the body's defense against oxidative stress [3].

Terminalia catappa, with its remarkable ecological resilience and rich nutritional and medicinal properties, offers a unique opportunity to address the growing challenges of global food

security and ecosystem stability, particularly in the current era of heightened emphasis on sustainable and climate-resilient agriculture [6]. The tree's ability to thrive in marginal conditions makes it an ideal candidate for cultivation in regions affected by climate stressors. Promoting the use of tropical almonds as a food source could help diversify diets, enhance nutrition, and provide a stable food supply in areas struggling with food scarcity. Furthermore, expanding its cultivation and market channels could support rural economies and foster agricultural biodiversity.

Despite its abundance and numerous benefits, *Terminalia catappa* remains significantly underutilised as a food resource. Factors such as limited public awareness about its edibility and the underdevelopment of processing and marketing systems have led to its classification as a neglected crop [3]. In contrast to the widely cultivated *Prunus dulcis*, the tropical almond receives minimal attention from food industries and agricultural stakeholders, restricting its integration into mainstream markets [3, 7]. In Nigeria, almond cultivation has not progressed to a commercial scale [1, 8]. Although almond trees are widespread across the country, fresh almonds are rarely found in local markets; only processed varieties imported from other countries are available for sale [1].

Several studies have examined the nutritional properties of *Terminalia catappa* fruit, focusing on the fruit's kernel and its oil [3, 4, 5, 9, 10, 11]. In contrast, the fruit's hull (the outer covering of the fruit) has received very little attention from researchers. The aim of this study was therefore to assess the health and nutritional quality of *Terminalia catappa* hull collected at three different locations in Lagos, Nigeria.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study area

The study was conducted in Yaba, Lagos State, Nigeria, a humid tropical area with diverse vegetation, including freshwater swamp forests, mangrove swamps, sandy plains, and disturbed secondary rainforest, shaped by its proximity to the Lagos Lagoon and human activities [12]. Yaba hosts three federal higher institutions which include the University of Lagos, the Federal College of Education, and Yaba College of Technology, which significantly influence its land-use dynamics [12].

2.2 Sample collection

Wild varieties of *Terminalia catappa* trees that naturally grow in the study area were sampled, three in each institution (University of Lagos, the Federal College of Education, and Yaba College of Technology). For the study, one unripe almond fruit was plucked from each sampled tree. The specific sampling sites in each location were as follows: Indomie Bridge, Lagoon Front, and Faculty of Science in the University of Lagos; School Gate, Moyisola MM Adenubi Building, and the College Technical Fire Plant in the Federal College of Education, Akoka; and Yaba Tech Gate, Yaba Tech Sports Centre, and Yaba Tech Roundabout in Yaba College of Technology. A total of nine unripe almond fruits were collected, with one unripe fruit taken from each of the three trees across the three institutions. The fruits were identified and authenticated by plant taxonomists in the University of Lagos and then taken to the laboratory for nutrient, proximate, and phytochemical composition analysis. The sampling locations and sites are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Locations, and geographical coordinates of sample collection sites.

Institution	Sampling site	Coordinate
University of Lagos, Yaba.	Indomie Bridge	6.2754°N, 3.2567°E
	Lagoon Front	6.3281°N, 3.2999°E
	Faculty of Science	6.4012°N, 3.3325°E
Federal College of Education, Yaba	School Gate	6.5231°N, 3.3819°E
	Moyisola MM Adenubi Building	6.5197°N, 3.3855°E
	College Technical Fire Plant	6.5228°N, 3.3842°E
Yaba College of Technology, Yaba	Yaba Tech Gate	6.5192°N, 3.3738°E
	Yaba Tech Sports Centre	6.5179°N, 3.3751°E
	Yaba Tech Roundabout	6.5183°N, 3.3746°E

2.3 Proximate analysis of almond (*Terminalia catappa*) hulls

The proximate composition (moisture content, carbohydrate, protein, lipid, ash, and crude fibre levels) of *Terminalia catappa* hull samples was determined following the guidelines established by the Association of Official Analytical Chemists [13]. The hulls of the collected fruit samples were peeled and homogenised. Total nitrogen content was measured using the Micro Kjeldahl method, as shown in equation 1, with protein content calculated by multiplying the nitrogen value by a conversion factor of 6.25. Lipid content was quantified using Soxhlet extraction, while carbohydrate content was estimated as the remaining percentage after accounting for the measured components. Energy value was computed from the contributions of carbohydrates, lipids, and protein.

2.3.1 Protein content determination

The protein content of the almond samples was assessed using the micro-Kjeldahl method. Five grams (5g) of the sample was digested with concentrated sulphuric acid (H₂SO₄) and a Kjeldahl catalyst in a Kjeldahl flask for 4 hours. The resulting digest was diluted to 100 mL with distilled water. A 5 mL aliquot of the diluted solution was transferred to a Kjeldahl apparatus, and 5 mL of 40% (w/v) sodium hydroxide (NaOH) solution was added. The mixture was steam-distilled, releasing ammonia gas, which was captured in 10 mL of 2% boric acid. The distillate was titrated against a 0.01 M hydrochloric acid (HCl) solution. The percentage nitrogen of each sample was calculated (as shown in equation 1) from which the crude protein content of each sample was calculated by multiplying the percentage of nitrogen obtained by a factor of 6.25, as shown in equation 2.

$$\%Nitrogen = \frac{Xmoles}{100cm^3} * \frac{Vs-Vb}{mg} * \frac{14g}{Moles} * 100 \quad \text{--- (1)}$$

Where:

Vs and Vb are titration volumes of sample and blanks, and fourteen grams (14g) in the molecular weight of nitrogen N.A blank sample was run concurrently with the test sample to account for any residual nitrogen present in the reagents used during the analysis. After determining the nitrogen content, it was converted into protein content using the appropriate conversion factor:

$$Protein\ content = F\ (\%N) \text{-----} (2)$$

2.3.2 Lipid content determination

Five grams (5 g) of the dried, powdered sample was weighed into a fat-free extraction thimble, which was lightly plugged with cotton wool. The thimble was placed in a Soxhlet extractor equipped with a reflux condenser. The dried sample was extracted using petroleum ether as the solvent. The crude lipid content was calculated as grams per 100 grams (g/100 g) of the dry sample weight and subsequently converted to grams per 100 grams (g/100 g) of the fresh sample weight. The percentage lipid was therefore determined using equation 3.

$$\%Lipid = 100 * \frac{M\ lipid}{M\ sample} \text{-----} (3)$$

Where: M sample = Initial sample;

M lipid = Mass of the lipid remaining after the solvent is evaporated.

2.3.3 Ash content determination

The ash content was determined by weighing 5 grams (5 g) of each sample and heating it in a muffle furnace at 550°C for 4 hours. After heating, the sample was cooled to approximately 100°C within the furnace and then transferred to a desiccator to cool to room temperature. The sample was reweighed, and the ash content was calculated as grams per 100 grams (g/100 g) of the original sample. The concentration of ash present was determined using the dry ashing technique by comparing the sample's weight before and after washing. The ash content of food was calculated using equation 4.

$$\%Ash\ (dry\ basis) = 100 * \frac{M\ as}{M\ dry} \text{-----} (4)$$

Where: M Ash = mass of the ashed samples;

M Dry = original mass of the dried samples.

2.3.4 Moisture content determination

A 5-gram (5.0 g) portion of the crushed sample was placed in a clean, pre-weighed crucible that had been previously ignited. The crucible containing the sample was heated in an oven at 105°C until a constant weight was achieved over a duration of 46 hours. After heating, the crucible was removed, cooled in a desiccator, and then

weighed. The percentage moisture content of the sample was calculated using equation 5:

$$\% \text{ Moisture} = 100 * \frac{W2-W3}{W1-W0} \text{-----} (5)$$

Where; W0 = weight of the sample;

W1 = weight of the empty crucible in grams;

W2 = weight of the crucible dish and the sample before oven drying; and

W3 = weight of the crucible dish and the sample after oven drying.

2.3.5 Crude fibre content determination

Crude fibre composition of samples was determined by method described by Egbuna *et al.* [13]. 2–3 g of sample was weighed and added to 200 mL boiling solution of 1.25% sulfuric acid. The 5–6 drops of antifoam was added to the solution and then brought to boiling within 1–2 min. The solution was boiled gently for exactly 30 min, maintaining the volume of distilled water constant and swirling the flask periodically to remove particles adhering to the sides. The Buchner funnel was set up with filter paper and pre-heat with boiling water. At the same time, at the end of the boiling period, the flask was removed and left to rest for 1 min and contents filtered carefully, using suction. The filter paper was then washed with boiling water. For the second time, the residue in the flask was transferred and boiled for 30 min using 200 mL of boiling NaOH solution. After boiling, it was allowed to stand for 1 min. the hydrolyzed mixture was then filtered into a crucible that was preheated with boiling water and dried. The residue obtained was washed with boiling water and the water discarded. Residue was then washed with HCl solution and again with boiling water and discard. It was the wash thrice with petroleum ether. The crucible was then placed in an oven (105°C) for 12 hours, and then cooled in a dryer. The weight of the crucible with the residue inside was obtained (W2) before placing the crucible with content in the furnace at 550°C for 3 hours for ashing. After ashing, it was left to cool in a dryer and weigh again (W1). The crude fiber composition was then calculated using equation 6.

$$\% \text{ Crude fibre} = \frac{W2-W2}{\text{Weigh of sample}} * 100 \text{-----} (6)$$

2.3.6 Carbohydrate content determination

The total carbohydrate content of the sample was calculated by adding the percentage values of the other measured components, including moisture, crude protein, crude fibre, lipid, and ash. The sum was then subtracted from 100 to obtain the carbohydrate content, using equation 7

$$\text{Carbohydrate Content (\%)} = 100 - (\text{Moisture} + \text{Crude Protein} + \text{Crude Fibre} + \text{Lipid} + \text{Ash}) \text{---} (7)$$

2.4 Qualitative analysis of phytochemicals in *Terminalia catappa* hull

2.4.1 Test for anthraquinones

Borntrager's Test (for Free Anthracene Derivatives): To determine the presence of free anthraquinones, 0.5 g of the powdered sample was mixed with 5 mL of chloroform, shaken vigorously for 5 minutes, and filtered. An equal volume of 10% ammonia solution was added to the filtrate. The presence of a pink, red, or violet colour in the aqueous layer after shaking indicated free anthraquinones [15].

2.4.2 Test for steroids

Salkowski Test: In a 2 mL aqueous extract, 2 mL of chloroform and 2 mL of sulphuric acid were added and shaken well. The development of a red chloroform layer and greenish-yellow fluorescence in the acid layer confirmed the presence of steroids [16].

2.4.3 Test for terpenoids

To 3 mL of the extract, 2 mL of chloroform was added and evaporated to dryness. The residue was treated with 2 mL of concentrated sulphuric acid and heated for 2 minutes. A greyish colour formation confirmed the presence of terpenoids [17].

2.4.4 Test for triterpenoids

Noller's Test: The extract was warmed with tin and thionyl chloride. A purple coloration confirmed the presence of triterpenoids [18].

2.4.5 Test for glycosides

Borntrager's Test: To 3 mL of the aqueous extract, dilute sulphuric acid was added, boiled, and filtered. The filtrate was treated with an equal volume of benzene and shaken. The organic layer

was decanted, and dilute ammonia solution was added. A pink colour in the ammonia layer indicated the presence of glycosides [19].

2.4.6 Test for carbohydrates

Molisch's Test: Few drops of Molisch's reagent were added to the extract dissolved in distilled water. Then, 1 mL of concentrated sulphuric acid was added along the side of the test tube. A red or dull violet colour at the interface confirmed the presence of carbohydrates [15].

2.4.7 Test for reducing sugars

Fehling's Test: The test samples were mixed with equal volumes of Fehling's A and B solutions and heated in a water bath. A red colour indicated the presence of reducing sugars [18].

2.4.8 Test for tannins

To 5 mL of the extract, a few drops of lead acetate were added. The formation of a yellow precipitate confirmed the presence of tannins [19].

2.4.9 Test for saponins

Twenty millilitres (20 mL) of distilled water were added to the extract in a graduated cylinder and shaken vigorously for 15 minutes. A foam layer approximately 1 cm thick indicated the presence of saponins [20].

2.4.10 Test for flavonoids

To 5 mL of dilute ammonia solution, the sample extract was added, followed by concentrated sulphuric acid. The appearance of a yellow colour that disappeared confirmed the presence of flavonoids [21].

2.4.11 Test for alkaloids

To the extract, 1% hydrochloric acid and six drops of Meyer's reagent and Dragendorff's reagent were added. The formation of an organic precipitate indicated the presence of alkaloids [20].

2.4.12 Test for cyanides

To 1 mL of the extract, 15 mL of distilled water was added in a test tube. Alkaline picrate paper was suspended over the mixture and sealed with a rubber bung for 18 hours at room temperature. A change in colour from yellow to reddish-brown indicated the presence of cyanides [21].

2.4.13 Test for phenols

Ferric Chloride Test (Brayer's Test): To the extract, 3–4 drops of ferric chloride solution were added. A bluish-black colour confirmed the presence of phenols [22].

2.4.14 Test for anthocyanins

To 2 mL of the aqueous extract, 2 mL of 2N hydrochloric acid and ammonia were added. The appearance of a pink-red colour that turned blue-violet indicated the presence of anthocyanins [16].

2.4.15 Test for phlobatannins

To 2 mL of the sample extract, 3 mL of distilled water was added and filtered. A few millilitres of 2% hydrochloric acid were added to the filtrate, and the mixture was heated to boiling. A red precipitate indicated the presence of phlobatannins [16].

2.5 Quantitative analysis of phytochemical constituents of *Terminalia catappa* hulls

2.5.1 Total phenolic content

Total phenolic content (TPC) was determined using the Folin-Ciocalteu reagent method with slight modifications as described by Tasmim *et al.* [23]. The reaction mixture was prepared by combining 0.5 mL of the ethanolic extract, 2.5 mL of 10% Folin-Ciocalteu reagent dissolved in water, and 2.5 mL of 7.5% sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO₃). A blank solution was prepared using Folin-Ciocalteu reagent dissolved in water and 2.5 mL of 7.5% NaHCO₃ without the extract.

For the standard curve, gallic acid was used, and several dilutions of gallic acid in 80% ethanol were prepared at concentrations of 20, 40, 60, 80, and 100 µg/mL. A 1.0 mL aliquot of each dilution was taken in test tubes and diluted with 10 mL of distilled water. Then, 2.5 mL of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent was added, followed by 2.5 mL of 7.5% NaHCO₃. The mixture was left to stand for 30 minutes at room temperature.

Absorbance measurements for the standard and samples were taken at 765 nm using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer against the blank. The concentration of total phenolics in the extracts was expressed as milligrams of gallic acid equivalent per gram (mg GAE/g) of the extract. The total phenolic content was calculated using equation 8.

$$\text{Total phenolic content} = \text{GAE} * \text{V} * \text{D}/\text{W} \text{-----} (8)$$

Where, GAE is the gallic acid equivalent (mg/g);

V is the volume of extract (mL),

D is dilution factor and

W is the weight (g) of the pure plant extract.

2.5.2 Total alkaloid content in almond (*Terminalia catappa*) hulls

The total alkaloid content of the samples was determined using the standard procedures described by Krishnaiah *et al.* [24]. Five grams (5 g) of the plant sample was prepared in a beaker, and 200 mL of 10% acetic acid in ethanol was added. The mixture was covered and allowed to stand for 4 hours. It was then filtered, and the filtrate was concentrated in a water bath until it reached one-quarter of its original volume. Concentrated ammonium hydroxide (NH₄OH) was added dropwise until the precipitation was complete. The solution was allowed to settle, and the precipitate was collected, washed with dilute NH₄OH, filtered, and dried. The dried residue, representing the total alkaloid content, was then weighed.

2.5.3 Total tannin content in almond (*Terminalia catappa*) hulls

The total tannin content of the samples was determined using the spectrophotometric method as outlined by Krishnaiah *et al.* [24]. A 0.5 g sample of the plant material was weighed into a 50 mL plastic bottle, and 50 mL of distilled water was added. The mixture was stirred for 1 hour and filtered into a 50 mL volumetric flask, which was then made up to the mark with distilled water. Five millilitres (5 mL) of the filtrate was pipetted into a test tube and mixed with 2 mL of 0.1 M ferric chloride (FeCl₃) in 0.1 M hydrochloric acid (HCl) and 0.008 M potassium ferricyanide [K₄Fe(CN)₆·3H₂O]. The absorbance of the resulting mixture was measured at 395 nm using a spectrophotometer within 10 minutes.

2.5.4 Total saponin content in almond (*Terminalia catappa*) hulls

The total saponin content of the samples was determined according to the standard procedures of Krishnaiah *et al.* [24]. Twenty grams (20 g) of each ground plant sample was placed in a conical flask, and 100 mL of 20% ethanol was added. The

sample was heated over a hot water bath at approximately 55°C for 4 hours with continuous stirring. The mixture was filtered, and the residue was re-extracted with an additional 200 mL of 20% ethanol. The combined extracts were concentrated to 40 mL using a water bath at approximately 90°C. The concentrate was transferred to a 250 mL separator funnel, and 20 mL of diethyl ether was added. After vigorous shaking, the aqueous layer was recovered, and the diethyl ether layer was discarded. The purification process was repeated, and 60 mL of n-butanol was added. The combined n-butanol extracts were washed twice with 10 mL of 5% sodium chloride (NaCl). The remaining solution was evaporated in a water bath, and the residue was dried in an oven to a constant weight.

2.5.5 Total flavonoid content in almond (*Terminalia catappa*) hulls

The spectrophotometric method described by Tasmim *et al.* [23] was used to determine the total flavonoid content. One millilitre (1 mL) of the ethanolic extract (at a concentration of 1 mg/mL) was mixed with 1 mL of 2% aluminium chloride (AlCl₃) in ethanol. The mixture was incubated at room temperature for 1 hour. The absorbance was then measured at 415 nm using a spectrophotometer. The total flavonoid content was estimated in terms of quercetin equivalent from the plant extracts using equation 9.

$$\text{Flavonoids content} = (\text{QE} * \text{V} * \text{DF})/\text{W} \text{-----} (9)$$

Where, QE = quercetin equivalent (mg QE/g),

V = total volume of sample (mL),

DF = dilution factor, and

W = samples weight (g).

2.5.6 Total phytate content in almond (*Terminalia catappa*) hulls

Total phytate content was determined using the standard method described by Ekpa [25]. A 0.2 g portion of the sample was accurately weighed into a 250 mL conical flask and soaked in 100 mL of 20% concentrated hydrochloric acid (HCl) for 3 hours. The mixture was then filtered, and 50 mL of the filtrate was transferred into a 250 mL beaker. Subsequently, 100 mL of distilled water was added to the filtrate, followed by the addition of 10 mL of 0.3% ammonium thiocyanate solution as an indicator. The sample was titrated with a standard iron (III) chloride solution containing 0.00195 g of

iron per mL. The phytate content was then calculated using equation 10.

$$\text{Phytate content} = \frac{\text{Titre value} \times 0.00195 \times 1.19 \times 100}{2} \quad (10)$$

2.5.7 Total glycosides content in almond (*Terminalia catappa*) hulls

Total glycosides content was determined following the method described by Muhammad *et al.* [26]. 4g of the solid sample was weighed, homogenised in 20 mL of water, and filtered to obtain a liquid extract for analysis. Eight millilitres (8 mL) of plant extract were transferred into a 100 mL volumetric flask, to which 60 mL of water and 8 mL of 12.5% lead acetate solution were added. The mixture was thoroughly mixed and filtered. Fifty millilitres (50 mL) of the filtrate were then transferred into another 100 mL volumetric flask, and 8 mL of 47% disodium hydrogen phosphate (Na_2HPO_4) solution were added to precipitate excess Pb^{2+} ions. The solution was mixed and brought up to volume with water. The resulting mixture was filtered twice through the same filter paper to remove any residual lead phosphate. Subsequently, 10 mL of the purified filtrate was transferred into a clean Erlenmeyer flask and treated with 10 mL of Baljet reagent. A blank titration was performed using 10 mL of distilled water and 10 mL of Baljet reagent. Both solutions were allowed to stand for one hour to ensure complete colour development. The intensity of the developed colour was measured colorimetrically at a wavelength of 495 nm and estimated using equation 11.

$$\text{Glycoside Content (mg/100 g)} = \frac{A_{\text{std}}}{A_{\text{s}}} \times \text{Cstd} \times \frac{W_{\text{s}}}{V_{\text{e}}} \times 100 \quad (11)$$

Where:

As: Absorbance of the sample measured at 495 nm.

Astd: Absorbance of the standard solution measured at 495 nm.

Cstd: Concentration of the standard solution (mg/mL).

Ve: Volume of the extract used in the analysis (mL).

Ws: Weight of the sample used for the extraction (g).

2.6 Mineral assay in almond (*Terminalia catappa*) hulls

The mineral assay followed the procedures outlined in AOAC [13] using an Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS). Fifty grams (50 g) of plant tissue were collected from each fruit sample, and all samples were thoroughly washed first with tap water and then with deionised distilled water. The samples were cut into small pieces and sun-dried on a concrete floor for approximately 12 hours. Once dried, the samples were ground into a powdered form.

For digestion, approximately 0.5 g of each powdered sample, in duplicate, was placed into digestion tubes. To each tube, 5 mL of nitric acid (HNO_3) and 2.5 mL of perchloric acid (HClO_4) were added in a 2:1 ratio and mixed thoroughly. The tubes were heated in a boiling water bath at approximately 100°C for 10–12 hours and then cooled. Subsequently, an additional 2.5 mL of nitric acid was added to each tube, and the solutions were heated in a boiling water bath for another 3–4 hours until they became transparent.

The digested solutions were cooled and filtered through Whatman No. 1 filter paper, then diluted to a final volume of 100 mL with deionised distilled water to create working standards. All glassware, including digestion tubes, was pre-soaked in 30% nitric acid for 8 hours and thoroughly rinsed with deionised distilled water before use.

For analysis, an aliquot of 14 mL from each treatment solution was pipetted into test tubes. A reagent blank was prepared by placing 14 mL of deionised distilled water into a separate test tube. The absorbance and concentrations (ppm) of the minerals were measured using AAS at the following wavelengths: iron (Fe) at 371.99 nm, zinc (Zn) at 307.59 nm, potassium (K) at 766.5 nm, calcium (Ca) at 422.7 nm, and magnesium (Mg) at 285.2 nm. The mineral content in the plant extract was calculated based on the concentrations (ppm) obtained from the solutions using equation 12.

$$\text{The percentage of minerals (Mg/kg of fresh plant)} = \frac{C \times V \times P \times \text{TPW}}{W \times \text{Mg} \times P} * DF \quad (12)$$

Where, C = Concentrations (ppm) of the solutions;

V = Volume of stock solutions;

P = Percentage;

W = Weight (g) of used powder;
Mg = Milligram factor;
DF = Dilation factor and
TPW = Total powder weight (in g) obtained from
1000 g sample.

2.7 Statistical analysis

The data generated from the study were analysed using One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to evaluate the differences in nutritional and phytochemical contents of *Terminalia catappa* hulls across the sampling locations. The analysis was performed using SPSS v 27 statistical software (IBM Corp., USA). Statistical significance was determined at a threshold of $p \leq 0.01$ and $p \leq 0.05$. Results were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) for all variables.

3.0 Result

Table 2: Proximate composition of *Terminalia catappa* hulls

PROXIMATE	UNILAG	FCE	Yaba Tech	F
Moisture %	66.41 \pm 22.07 ^a	71.10 \pm 0.33 ^a	71.88 \pm 0.07 ^a	0.49 ^{ns}
Protein %	1.61 \pm 0.03 ^a	1.52 \pm 0.03 ^b	1.43 \pm 0.03 ^c	71.91 ^{**}
Ash %	4.30 \pm 0.04 ^a	4.00 \pm 0.03 ^c	4.24 \pm 0.04 ^b	153.97 ^{**}
Fat %	0.46 \pm 0.02 ^b	0.41 \pm 0.02 ^a	0.47 \pm 0.02 ^a	20.41 ^{**}
Crude Fibre %	2.90 \pm 0.05 ^a	2.64 \pm 0.05 ^c	2.80 \pm 0.05 ^b	62.86 ^{**}
Carbohydrates %	24.32 \pm 0.05 ^a	20.36 \pm 0.40 ^a	19.16 \pm 0.11 ^a	0.41 ^{ns}

Value (mean \pm standard deviation, n = 3) in the same row with different superscripts are significantly different (** $P < 0.01$, ns: not significant); UNILAG: University of Lagos, Akoka, Yaba, Lagos State; FCE: Federal College of Education, Akoka, Lagos State; YABA TECH: Yaba College of Technology, Yaba, Lagos State

3.2 Mineral contents of *Terminalia catappa* hulls across sampling locations

The mineral levels of *Terminalia catappa* hulls were significantly different ($P < 0.01$) across the three groups (UNILAG, FCE and Yaba Tech), as shown in Table 3. UNILAG almond had the highest calcium (19.23 \pm 0.51 mg/100g) and zinc (0.87 \pm 0.01 mg/100g) and the least potassium

3.1 Proximate composition of *Terminalia catappa* hulls across locations

Results of proximate analysis presented in Table 2 showed no significant differences observed in moisture and carbohydrate of almond hulls in the three sampling locations; University of Lagos (UNILAG), Federal College of Education (FCE) and Yaba College of Technology (Yaba Tech). Almond hulls in UNILAG had the highest Protein (1.61 \pm 0.03 %), likewise ash (4.30 \pm 0.04%), and crude fiber (2.90 \pm 0.05). Yaba Tech had the least protein (1.43 \pm 0.03). Almond at FCE had the least ash (4.00 \pm 0.03 %) and crude fibre (2.64 \pm 0.05 %). There was no significant difference between fat in almond at FCE and almond at Yaba Tech (Table 2).

(165.92 \pm 2.25 mg/100g). Yaba Tech almond had the highest Iron (6.71 \pm 0.12 mg/100g) and the least calcium (17.21 \pm 0.31 mg/100g). FCE had the least for all the minerals (Vitamin A: 0.03 \pm 0.01 mg/100g, Vitamin C: 75.45 \pm 1.52 mg/100g, Calcium: 17.97 \pm 0.24 mg/100g, Zinc: 0.76 \pm 0.01 mg/100g, Iron: 7.17 \pm 1.26 mg/100g, Potassium: 167.85 \pm 1.32 mg/100g, Magnesium: 8.56 \pm 0.08 mg/100g (Table 3).

Table 3: Mineral contents of *Terminalia catappa* hulls across sampling locations

MINERALS	UNILAG	FCE	Yaba Tech	F
Vitamin A (mg/100g)	0.36 \pm 0.01 ^a	0.03 \pm 0.01 ^b	0.03 \pm 0.01 ^a	10.38 ^{**}
Vitamin C (mg/100g)	762.46 \pm 5.22 ^b	75.45 \pm 1.52 ^b	77.76 \pm 0.32 ^a	13.90 ^{**}
Calcium (Ca) (mg/100g)	19.23 \pm 0.51 ^a	17.97 \pm 0.24 ^b	17.21 \pm 0.31 ^c	66.04 ^{**}
Zinc (Zn) (mg/100g)	0.87 \pm 0.01 ^a	0.76 \pm 0.01 ^c	0.78 \pm 0.09 ^b	126.38 ^{**}
Iron (Fe) (mg/100g)	6.71 \pm 0.12 ^c	7.17 \pm 0.12 ^b	7.42 \pm 0.07 ^a	91.76 ^{**}
Potassium (K) (mg/100g)	165.92 \pm 2.25 ^c	167.85 \pm 1.32 ^b	174.03 \pm 1.30 ^a	56.62 ^{**}
Magnesium (Mg) (mg/100g)	8.74 \pm 0.09 ^a	8.56 \pm 0.08 ^b	8.81 \pm 0.05 ^a	23.10 ^{**}

Value (mean \pm standard deviation, n = 3) in the same row with different superscripts are significantly different (** $P < 0.01$); UNILAG: University of Lagos, Akoka, Yaba, Lagos State; FCE: Federal College of Education, Akoka, Lagos State; YABA TECH: Yaba College of Technology, Yaba, Lagos State.

3.3 Qualitative phytochemical assessment of *Terminalia catappa* hulls across locations

The heatmap (Figure 1) illustrates the phytochemical profiles of samples from FCE, UNILAG, and Yaba Tech, revealing consistent patterns and some variations. Tannins, anthraquinones, carbohydrates, glycosides, alkaloids, and phenolic compounds are abundantly

present (++) across all samples, while flavonoids show abundance in FCE and Yaba Tech (++) , but moderate presence in UNILAG (+). Saponins and reducing sugars are moderately present (+) in all samples, whereas steroids, phlobatanins, terpenoids, triterpenoids, and cyanide are absent (-) across the board. Anthocyanins are abundant in FCE and Yaba Tech (++) , but moderately present in UNILAG (+).

Figure 1: Heatmap of phytochemical presence in *Terminalia catappa* hulls across locations.

Green and red signify the presence and absence of phytochemicals, respectively.

3.4 Phytochemical contents of *Terminalia catappa* hulls across locations

Table 4 shows the levels of phytochemicals in *Terminalia catappa* hulls across the sampling locations. Reducing sugar and phytates across the three locations were not significantly different ($P > 0.05$). Almond fruits in Yaba Tech had the significant highest quantities of phytochemicals.

UNILAG almond hulls had the least tannins (4.49 ± 0.06 mg/100g), saponin (0.48 ± 0.02 mg/100g), alkaloids (1.25 ± 0.03 mg/100g), glycosides (0.20 ± 0.02 mg/100g), and phenols (41.92 ± 2.86 mgGAE/100g). The least Anthocyanins (1.19 ± 0.10 mg/100g) were observed in the almond hulls at FCE. The average anthocyanins content (1.46 ± 0.09 mg/100g) in almond hulls at FCE was the least, compared with other locations (Table 4).

Table 4: Phytochemical contents of *Terminalia catappa* hulls across locations

Phytochemical	UNILAG	FCE	Yaba Tech	F
Tannins (mg/100g)	4.49 ± 0.06 ^b	5.87 ± 0.46 ^a	5.49 ± 0.72 ^a	18.76**
Saponins (mg/100g)	0.48 ± 0.02 ^b	0.53 ± 0.02 ^a	0.55 ± 0.03 ^a	22.52**
Flavonoids (mgQE/100g)	1.18 ± 0.04 ^b	1.23 ± 0.02 ^{ab}	1.21 ± 0.04 ^a	5.84**
Alkaloids (mg/100g)	1.25 ± 0.03 ^c	1.32 ± 0.06 ^b	1.40 ± 0.02 ^a	32.41**
Glycosides (mg/100g)	0.20 ± 0.02 ^b	0.25 ± 0.02 ^a	0.25 ± 0.02 ^a	12.78**
Phytates (mg/100g)	0.22 ± 0.04 ^a	0.24 ± 0.02 ^a	0.23 ± 0.04 ^a	0.81 ^{ns}
Phenols (mgGAE/100g)	41.92 ± 2.86 ^c	48.19 ± 4.30 ^b	56.26 ± 1.47 ^a	48.42**
Anthraquinones (mg/100g)	0.15 ± 0.02 ^b	0.16 ± 0.03 ^b	0.22 ± 0.03 ^a	16.30**
Carbohydrates (mg/100g)	5.72 ± 0.14 ^b	5.67 ± 0.14 ^b	6.11 ± 0.25 ^a	15.08**
Reducing Sugars (mg/100g)	3.24 ± 0.24 ^a	3.32 ± 0.32 ^a	3.84 ± 1.06 ^a	2.29 ^{ns}
Anthocyanins (mg/100g)	1.46 ± 0.09 ^a	1.19 ± 0.10 ^b	1.43 ± 0.10 ^a	21.20**

Value (mean ± standard deviation, n = 3) in the same row with different superscripts are significantly different (** $P < 0.01$, * $P < 0.05$); UNILAG: University of Lagos, Akoka, Yaba, Lagos State; FCE: Federal College of Education, Akoka, Lagos State; YABA TECH: Yaba College of Technology, Yaba, Lagos State

4.0 Discussion

The proximate composition of *Terminalia catappa* hulls demonstrated significant variation across the three sampling locations. The observed moisture content in the hulls was substantially higher than previously reported values for the fruit kernel, as documented by Akpabio [27] and Siqueira *et al.* [28], who reported average moisture levels of 25% and 8%, respectively. This higher moisture levels may be attributed to the hull's structure, which is likely to retain more water due to its fibrous nature. However, the carbohydrate composition of the hulls in this study (ranging from 19% to 24%) was comparable to the carbohydrate content of the kernel reported by Akpabio [27] and Siqueira *et al.* [28], both of which were within the range of 20%–30%.

Crude fibre levels observed in *Terminalia catappa* hulls were consistent with the amounts of crude fibre in the tropical almond kernel reported by Akpabio [27] (approximately 3%) but diverged from the higher levels reported by Siqueira *et al.* [28] and the lower values noted by Olatidoye *et al.* [10]. Similarly, the fat content of the hulls aligned with the values reported by Olatidoye *et al.* [10] but was lower than the levels documented by Akpabio [27] and Siqueira *et al.* [28]. The protein content of the hulls was generally low compared to the kernel reported in earlier studies, reflecting the composition of the outer covering of the fruit, which is less nutrient-dense than the kernel.

The results indicate that environmental and growth-influencing factors specific to each location may play a critical role in shaping the nutritional profile of *Terminalia catappa* hulls. This is consistent with Pant *et al.* [29], who emphasized that variations in local environmental

conditions such as temperature, carbon dioxide, lighting, ozone, soil water, soil salinity and soil fertility significantly influence plant quality. The significant differences in proximate parameters such as protein, crude fibre, and ash content across the three locations, as observed in this study, further underscore the impact of these factors.

Regarding mineral content, the hulls were found to contain low amounts of vitamin A but high levels of vitamin C and minerals such as calcium, zinc, iron, potassium, and magnesium. These findings align with those of Akpabio [27], Siqueira *et al.* [28] and Yada *et al.* [30], who also reported substantial vitamin and mineral content in *Terminalia catappa*. However, the hulls do not meet the daily recommended dietary allowances (RDAs) for nutrients such as vitamin A (0.526 mg), calcium (200 – 250mg), zinc (12mg), iron (300mg), potassium (1,600 - 2,000mg), and magnesium (26mg), as outlined by the National Research Council [31]. Nonetheless, the vitamin C content of the hulls exceeds the RDA of 60 mg for adults, indicating that *Terminalia catappa* hulls could serve as a rich source of this essential nutrient.

Phytochemical analysis revealed the presence of bioactive compounds such as tannins, saponins, flavonoids, alkaloids, glycosides, phytates, phenols, anthraquinones, carbohydrates, reducing sugars, and anthocyanins across all locations. This was consistent with findings by Akpabio [27], Siqueira *et al.* [28], and Prgomet *et al.* [32], who also identified similar phytochemicals in *Terminalia catappa*. Phytochemicals are highly beneficial to the human body as they support immune function, protect cells and DNA from damage that could lead to cancer, reduce inflammation, slow the growth of certain cancer

cells, and help regulate hormones [32, 33]. The absence of cyanides, steroids, terpenoids, triterpenoids, and phlobatannins across all locations suggests that *Terminalia catappa* hulls are free of potentially harmful phytochemicals, particularly cyanide, which could limit their applicability in food and pharmaceutical industries. Conversely, the presence of beneficial phytochemicals highlights the potential of the hulls to be utilized as functional food ingredients or nutraceuticals.

5.0 Conclusion

This study highlights the nutritional and medicinal potential of *Terminalia catappa* hulls, which are rich in bioactive compounds such as tannins, flavonoids, phenols, and anthocyanins. Notably, the hulls contain vitamin C in quantities exceeding daily adult requirements, while other nutrients, including calcium, zinc, and iron, are present in smaller amounts. The variation in nutrient and phytochemical levels across locations underscores the influence of environmental factors. While the hulls are not a significant source of certain essential nutrients, the phytochemical richness and high vitamin C content of the hulls suggest their potential use as a supplementary dietary resource and in other health-related applications. This research provides a foundation for further research into the functional properties and potential applications of *Terminalia catappa* hulls in addressing nutritional and health challenges.

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